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Margilan Intellectuals About The City Of New Margilan

Author(s), NODIRJON URAIMOVICH ABDULAKHATOV

Abstract:

This article discusses the memoirs of local Margilan historians associated with the city of Fergana, known as New Margilan, Skobelev, in the history of its formation as the central city of Ferghana region in the second half of the XIX century. The newly built regional center, New Margilan (Skobelev), was built as a city in Central Asia that embodied European achievements. In turn, there are places in the city that contradict the culture of the local population. For this reason, in the beginning, people who went to Skobelev to work were considered as “immoral” people. However, at the same time, the opening of scientific and cultural objects in the new city, landscaping attracted the attention of intellectuals. The historical significance of these memoirs is that they contain interesting information about the life of Russian intellectuals, whom the locals respected for their enlightenment and justice. The works of Abdulkadir Mahdum Nozik and Galib Margilani have not yet been published. If these works are published, New Margilan (Skobelev) may become one of the most important historical sources for researchers in the study of urban history.

Keywords: culture, value, memory, manuscript, change, system, interest, trader, attitude, intellectual, enlightenment,

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About Author

Author(s): NODIRJON URAIMOVICH ABDULAKHATOV

Candidate of historical sciences,
doctoral student international Islamic,
Academy of Uzbekistan, Uzbekistan.

E-Mail: (an_igp@mail.ru)

INTRODUCTION

By the second half of the 19th century, the Turkestan society experienced a very large political, social and economic changes. These changes are explained primarily by such factors as the capture of Turkestan, in particular in the Kokand Khanate and the annexation of the Fergana region to the tsarist empire, the introduction of a new system of political leadership, the penetration of new settlement capitalist relations into the society of the region, and a change in economic relations.

MAIN PART

The political situation of the middle of the 19th century occupies a special place in the history of the peoples of Central Asia. And also in this region the cultures, values and interests of the great powers came face to face. In most cases, these clashes took place in the form of political clashes, without the use of military force [1, p.22.].

Such a socio-political and economic situation could not but affect the situation and living standards of the population of the region. This can be seen on the example of the city of Fergana, founded in 1877 on the site of the village of "Sim". This is how the historian of Margilan Muhammad Aziz Margilani writes in his work "Tarihi Aziziy": "It was in 1876. The Russians came to Khukand. They bought the land of the village of Sum on the southern side of Margilan for gold, built a new city and named it "New Margilan".

Then different people from all sides came to the city of Fergana, the population grew, merchants and shops also became more and more. Wood has become expensive. Seeing this, everyone began to plant a lot of trees ... In 1898, a carriage, that is, a railway, came to Fergana. After the arrival of the railroad, many people of all nationalities and religions came to Fergana, the city was full of people, land prices became many times more expensive "[2, 72].

The city was originally called "New Margilan", it was located 12 km from the ancient city of Margilan. In 1907-1924 the city was renamed in honor of the Fergana regional military governor M. D. Skobelev (1843-1882), Skobelev - in the local pronunciation - was called "Iskobil". At the entrance to the park, built at that time by the sculptor A. Aubert, a volumetric bust measuring 76x62 cm of M.D.Skobelev was installed from bronze. At the moment, this bust is numbered KP. 11802 / s 623 is kept in the State Museum of History and Culture of the Fergana region.

The reason for the name of New Margilan by the name of M.D. Skobelev, it was the fact that he turned to the Governor-General of Turkestan K.P. von Kaufman with a request for the restoration of a new city near the Old City of Margilan and was able to get his approval. However, General M.D.Skobelev did not have the opportunity to see the new city. In March 1877 he was drafted to St. Petersburg in connection with the Balkan War. The newly built regional center has been erected in Central Asia as a city that embodies European achievements. In turn, the city has also opened entertainment options that contradict the vibrant culture of the local population. [3, 28].

Brothels were opened in the city of New Margilan, and prostitutes began to walk the streets of the city with open faces. According to V. Nalivkin, even religious scientists were invited to the opening of one of these immoral places [4238]. In the new Margilan Y. K. The brewing workshops of Bushman and A. V. Stefan worked [5,12]. As noted in the Turkiston

newspaper: "Of course, fanatics who are enemies of education and culture took advantage of this" [6,105].

At the beginning, there were cases when people who went to the city of Skobelev were called "morally spoiled." But at the same time, the opening of scientific and cultural centers in the new city, improvement work attracted the attention of the local intelligentsia.

Because, starting from the first period of construction of the new Margilan, great importance was attached to landscape works. According to the correspondence of the regional administration in 1877, on January 22, 285, under the responsibility of the head of the Margilan district, a strict ban was imposed on the purchase and felling of garden trees on the site of the newly built city. Since May 1877, Akhmed Sultanov was appointed to the position of "miroblik" to water the trees on the site of the city. Later he was also given an assistant.

An important role was played by seedling gardens, which were established in the city in 1877 with the aim of landscaping the city. For this, more than 16 acres of land have been allocated. There were not enough specialists with special skills to work here. Therefore, with the approval of the Governor-General, a foreign agronomist Karl Kopman was invited to Fergana.

Seedling gardens in Fergana have been supplying decorative and fruitful tree seedlings to other cities of Tashkent and Turkestan regions for 10 years. Sapling gardens also served as a research center. Since, 6 interns-students, sent from the city of Vernium, studied the science of gardening. In April 1879, the Fergana regional administration decided to build Fergana Avenue, plant trees on both sides of it, and restore the boulevards that separate the city from the military camp within the city [4, p.40].

As a result, rare species of seedlings and flowers were soon brought. Changes in the city, improvement works are described in memoirs, memoirs of local intelligentsia. However, these data have so far been ignored by their researchers. Abdulkadir Makhdum (1856-1914), a famous khattot, fakikh and historian who lived in the village of Kubbo of the Margilan bekstvo in the second half of the 19th and early 20th centuries, dastan "Gulnama", dedicated to the varieties of flowers brought to the city of New Margilan (Skobelev). This dastan describes more than fifty types of flowers planted in a new city, describes the features of each flower.

Abdulaziz kari Boltabaev (1900-1982), who worked under the pseudonym "Golib", was born in the city of Margilan. Golib Margilani studied at the old school from the age of six. Later, at the age of 15-18, he studied at the gymnasium in the city of Skobelev. In addition to his native language, he perfectly knew Arabic, Persian, Russian, was engaged in translation, accounting. Golib Margilani wrote a work called "Nasab", consisting of memoirs about Margilan. In this work, he talks about his student period in the city of Skobelev in the gymnasium.

He also brings information about the lifestyle of the inhabitants of this city: "General Skobelev took this fortress and built a city here. There used to be a small village called Siim (Siim-Persian silver). In the place where the bust of Marx stood, there was a bust of Skobelev. My elder brother Abdukhamid was a student of the gymnasium in Iskobil - Fergana. Later, he was diagnosed with tuberculosis. It must have been tuberculosis. Once my dad urgently took

my older brother to Tashkent, they returned a month later. As it turned out, the famous surgeon Barovskii operated on my brother Tashkent.

Golib Margilani wrote that the Sutyagin family accepted him as their own, and for several years they helped him a lot during his studies at the gymnasium. Thanks to this selfless help from them, Golib Margilaniy attracted the attention of even the governor-general as an excellent student of the Margilan gymnasium. He was also invited to visit the house of the Governor-General together with his teacher Alexander Petrovich.

In the memoirs of Golib Margilani, Maria Petrovna is described as a very kind and caring teacher. Especially the fact that Maria Petrovna fell ill, and even in the last minutes before her death, thoughts about the fate of Golib Margilaniy did not leave her very much vyapchatil him. For this reason, when he talks about his memories associated with the city of Skobelev, he will remember the Sutyagin family with great respect. An important aspect of Golib Margilani's life in the city of Skobelev is that he was able to courageously cope with the difficulties he faced, precisely thanks to the knowledge he received in the gymnasium.

CONCLUSION

The historical significance of these memoirs is that they contain interesting information about the life of Russian intellectuals, whom the local residents respected for their enlightenment and justice. The works of local historians Abdulkadir Makhdumov and Golib Margilani have not yet been published. When these works are published, New Margilan may become one of the most important historical sources for researchers in the study of the history of the city.

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